

Plan

This canvas is the starting point for planning your exploration of the future.

Recommendations for use:

a futures-thinking approach is divergent, so don't be afraid to think outside the box.

MACRO-THEME

What is the main theme?

Write the theme here.

SUB-THEMES

Narrow your research to specific topics related to the given macro-theme that you would like to explore (e.g., new gestures of affection, the artisan of the future, homes in 2050, gifts of the future, what our relationship with nature will be...).

1. _____

2. _____

3. _____

4. _____

5. _____

Full Name

Student ID number

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Megatrends Analysis

Full Name _____

This canvas allows you to analyze the impact of megatrends on the macro-theme of your research. You can add other megatrends that you consider relevant in the dotted spaces.

Student ID number

Then, for each megatrend, assign an impact score from 0 to 10.

Also, inside the boxes, explain why the megatrend you analyzed has an impact on the defined macro-theme.

Social inequalities

In my opinion, it has an impact because...

Urbanization

Demographic shifts

Climate change

Resource scarcity

Gender-related issues

Rapid technological advancement

10
9
8
7
6
5
4
3
2
1

Implications

Explore the direct and indirect implications of your **“What If”** question.

How to fill in the wheel:

1. Starting from the Megatrends Analysis, place at the center a question: “What would happen if...?”, taking into account the megatrend that would have the greatest impact for you. If necessary, consider multiple megatrends.

(Example question: what would happen if tomorrow flowers no longer existed?)

2. Then ask yourselves: what are the direct and/or indirect implications of this question? Fill in the wheel by listing the consequences: technological, environmental, social, economic and/or political.

After completing the wheel, it is possible to draw connections between the different domains.

Tip.

Use the ideas that seem most obvious and almost too simple. If you jump too far ahead at this stage, you'll miss important insights.

After completing the wheel:

indicate in the boxes the value of the implications you entered.

<p>The “good” <i>What is positive?</i></p>	<p>Who or what is mainly involved?</p>
<p>The “bad” <i>What is negative?</i></p>	<p>Who or what is mainly involved?</p>

Team Name _____

Storyboard

Devise and communicate a narrative sequence.

Building on the previous exercises (Megatrends and Implications), use the Storyboard canvas to represent, in sequence, the development of a scenario for your project and to describe your idea.

There are no constraints on the representation technique (freehand drawing, comic, illustration, render, generative images).

If you use AI (Artificial Intelligence), please indicate which system and prompts were used.

Tip.

Each scene will have its own board. Then, create a single PDF that groups them all together. We recommend producing at least 6 scenes.

Scene no. _____

Sketch

Scene description

Keywords

Characters

Scene goal

Change

Team Name

AI prompt (only if used)
